

ENERGY READ: A CO-CREATIVE WORKSHOP TOOL FOR DECISION MAKERS TO MAKE WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE MORE EFFECTIVE AND JUST

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ABOUT

In the wind energy transition, justice and effectiveness are either unfamiliar concepts, previously unused or do not have a sense of shared understanding. The compass is a co-creative workshop format to embed a shared understanding and create a future direction of wind energy development. Irrespective of scale (national strategy or project) or country.

KEY TOPICS

- Governance decision making tool for just and effective wind development
- Novel co-creative workshop format
- Tested in various settings with key regional stakeholders in four EU countries
- Strategies to improve justice and effectiveness in your country

GUIDELINES

Following in depth dialogue sessions with regional stakeholders we found that the concepts of justice and effectiveness are not universally understood nor applied. To make wind energy more just and effective it is therefore imperative to first **co-create a shared understanding of these concepts AND to formulate an ambition for the future.**

The compass is a workshop tool developed for the exact purpose. It is adaptable to various contexts, from local wind parks to international strategies/plans.

The compass is designed following 5 in depth dialogue sessions and 7 workshops across four different countries. Overall, it gave regional decision makers **more knowledge, competence and strategies** to improve upon **justice and effectiveness** in wind energy development.

THE METHOD IS AS FOLLOWS:

- 1 Setting a central theme/question, such as how might wind energy development look like in 2050 in the Netherlands?
- 2 Sensemaking, understanding and deciding on justice and effectiveness in the present context.
- 3 Setting ambitions, formulating goals for the future.
- 4 Identifying barriers to these ambitions.
- 5 Collecting strategies to overcome these barriers.

What is needed? An experienced facilitator, a local/regional expert on wind energy to set the central question and indicator.